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Teacher competences in relation to simulation-based training and learning

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Abstract

In an empirical-based research project about simulation-based training in the social and health care programs, one research question concerns the teachers' competences in relation to simulation-based training. The results of the analysis show that when comparing simulation-based training with classroom teaching, the teachers perceive the significant difference to be the role as facilitator. As a facilitator, the teacher has to develop and accept a new way of controlling the training situation, in which the teacher must be open towards unexpected issues and develop another attitude to teaching profession.

Keywords

simulation-based training; teacher competencies; social and health care programs

1 Introduction and research questions

The Danish social and health care programs show an increasing interest in simulation-based training and learning. During the last couple of years, the social- and healthcare colleges have been developing simulation environments including investing spectacular sums in simulation equipment, in particular mannequins. Furthermore, the colleges are currently trying out simulation pedagogy, i.e. how technologically based simulation should be conducted in order to support the students' motivation for learning as well as their learning outcome.

In a developmental project, (2017-2019) five social and health care colleges have developed and tested standards for simulation-based training. In the parallel research project, the aim is to provide empirical-based knowledge about the students' learning processes and learning outcome that can inspire further development of the standards and pinpoint the needs for teacher competences in relation to simulation-based training.

Simulation-based training shares the same kinds of challenges as other forms of practice-based learning. The most important challenge being that the students' learning processes and learning outcomes are in fact enhanced by choosing simulation-based training: As in other kinds of practice-based learning, the learning process in simulation-based training includes three phases:

1. Briefing which introduce relevant theory and the practical task in the scenario,
2. Scenario in which the students accomplish tasks in practice
3. Debriefing where the students reflect on the events of the scenario.

The paper focuses on teacher competences in relation to simulation-based training, posing the following research questions:

1. Which challenges do the teachers encounter when they carry out simulation-based training?
2. Which competences can be inferred from these challenges?

2 Brief literature review

Research into simulation-based training can be divided into the following main issues: accomplishing simulation-based training including degree of fidelity, activities in the phases of briefing and debriefing, the learners' outcome from simulation-based training, and the teachers' competences (Aarkrog, 2018 a; Aarkrog, 2018b). The paper focuses on teachers' competence.

The main research issues in relation to teacher competency, concern the teacher's ability to establishing a balance between being a professional performing in practice (i.e. playing the role as social and health care helper) and being a student (Sjöberg et al, 2015) including balancing fidelity with disruption of fidelity (Rooney et al., 2015), issues concerning the technology (the mannequin) (Winkel et al., 2014). The teacher's competences in relation to conducting the debriefing in a constructive tone and ensure 'psychological safety'. (Edmundson et al., 2016), including the ability for reflection (Flatgård & Berg, 2016). Finally, research includes the balance between the students' self-directedness and the teacher's directions. (Khaled et al., 2014; Kolbe et al., 2013; Lioce et al., 2015).

3 Method

The data collection employed observives, i.e. observations of the three phases of simulation-based training briefing, scenario, and debriefing followed by interviews with a group of four students and the teacher(s) who had participated in the observed simulation. At each of the five colleges (He, Ho, Ra, Si, and Sk) 1-2- observives were accomplished twice (spring and autumn, 2018). The interviews were recorded and transcribed.

4 Results

According to the interviewed teachers, the central role in relation to simulation-based training and learning is the role as facilitator. The role as facilitator differs from the role as teacher in various ways. One difference concerns the teacher's subject knowledge. The teacher prepares and accomplish the lesson, including the relevant theoretical knowledge and skills. The facilitator can expect the students to pose questions or make reflections that include knowledge that the facilitator need to brush up or do not know. "You have to let go of the role as an expert and accept that you do not know everything" (Teacher, Sk).

Another difference concerns the facilitator's scope of control. The facilitator has to be prepared for unexpected situations or questions. The role as teacher is familiar and consequently comfortable, "It is a matter about leaving the comfort zone when becoming a facilitator instead of a teacher. When you teach you are in control at the blackboard; as a facilitator... the students are the players... and one should be able to reflect together with the students" (Teacher, Ho). The facilitator assists the students reflecting on their actions in order that they reach the learning outcome targets. "The students should be more active, they should be heard. When I teach in the classroom, I have the role as the captain. As a facilitator, you can take several routes; I guide them to see various possibilities" (Teacher, Ho).

The several routes mean that the teachers have to be flexible and open to various issues. One of the teachers relates subject knowledge and flexibility, "You have to get your subject knowledge straight; or perhaps it is wrong to put it that way; it is a kind of flexibility. When I am in charge of the teaching I follow a structure; this (simulation-based training) asks for more flexibility; I am much more on my toes, more alert or alert in another way; I do not really know how to explain this." (Teacher Si). Flexibility means that the teachers feel that they as facilitators have to be better prepared than as teachers, "I must know my stuff, because

a lot of issues can be raised, e.g. working posture, communication. When you ask the students you have to be in control of your stuff” (Teacher, He).

In order to maintain control over the training situation the focus on the learning outcome target become particularly important, “The more the students bring in (into the debriefing) the better their learning outcome. E.g., one of the students said “We began by washing our hands with spirits” and I could have continued with this issue; there are so many issues. However, I had to focus on the learning outcome targets.” (Teacher Si). Thus the teacher controls the situation by filtering out topics that do not support reaching the learning outcome targets. This means that she will have to decline some of the topics brought up by the students, risking that the students can be hurt or demotivated for engaging in the debriefing. Thus, the teacher’s flexibility towards the students’ needs for discussing particular topics is challenged, because the teacher has to stick to the learning outcome targets.

A third difference is that reflection becomes a more central and natural tool particularly in the phase of debriefing. However, reflection and feedback are intertwined. The students ask for feedback and some of them even for grades; however, in the debriefing the aim is to avoid direct feedback in order that the students through reflections realize how they perform and how they can improve their performance. According to the teachers, it is difficult to establish a culture for reflection avoiding the direct feedback, “it is a matter of school culture; the culture has to be changed” (Teacher, Ra). Part of changing the culture includes that the teachers are skilled at reflecting together with the students. When the students are not able to reflect on their performance, the teachers need tools to qualify the reflections, “When Erna (the doll) has breathing difficulties and the student is not able to relate this to COPD, I am nervous to bring this up, not wanting to expose her in front of the classmates. I asked her, whether she would have performed differently next time, and she answered ‘no’! Okay, she might have had *some* reflections... such as, would there be other solutions? However, it is also risky to propose other solutions without assessing the students which may cause some (of the students) to think that this is not a pleasant situation anymore.”

Thus facilitating the students’ learning involve considerations about the students’ self-directedness: when and how much should the teacher interfere? “There is a risk that the students learn the wrong things; on the other side, there is not one correct answer... Better to feel safe and confident about finding a mutual solution” (Teacher Ra). However too much self-directedness might let down these students: “This group of students ask: What do you want us to do?” (Teacher, Ho). “They can cope with so little” Teacher Ra).

The role as facilitator calls for several competences; the teachers should be able to guide the students in reflection processes; the teacher should have social and personal competences, being flexible and open to the students’ needs for bringing up issues. The teachers should be able to invite the students to participate in a genuine reflection on practice while keeping the learning outcome targets in the students’ minds. However, most importantly the teachers should be able to change their attitudes about the proficient teacher who will be able to provide solid answers to all the students’ questions.

5 Discussion

Corresponding to previous research, mentioned above, the results in this project also point to the importance of establishing a psychologically safe environment for reflecting on practice and to the balance between the students’ self-directedness and the teacher’s directions of the students’ learning.

The role as facilitator gives raise to considerations about the teacher’s scope of control. On the one hand, the teacher should establish a milieu for reflecting about the students’ performance in the scenario, establishing psychological safety and be open to the students’ needs

for discussing various issues. On the other hand, the teacher wants to control the issues for reflection in order to appear well prepared.

Interestingly, the simulation-based training does not entail roles or competences that are not already relevant in relation to e.g. practice-based training or project work. These pedagogical principals have a rather long tradition in Danish VET. Even so, the role as facilitator seems to be a current challenge.

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Biographical notes

Vibe Aarkrog is an associate professor at the Danish School of Education, Aarhus University, researching pedagogy and didactics in vocational education and training with a focus on the interrelation of practice-based training and school-based training as well as on transfer of learning.